

**ECONOMIC SECURITY OF SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN****Z.A.Kaimova**Associate Professor, Department
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18264114>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 13th January 2026Accepted: 14th January 2026Online: 15th January 2026**KEYWORDS***economic security, integration, sustainable development, liberalization, global economic relations, foreign economic relations, risks and threats***ABSTRACT**

This paper proposes a theoretical and methodological justification for ensuring economic security from the perspective of the impact of threats on the national economy. The conceptual provisions for ensuring economic security proposed in this work are aimed at strengthening the position and promoting the Republic of Uzbekistan on the global stage.

The Sustainable Development Goals, adopted by the UN in 2015 as a universal action plan until 2030, represent a key national policy guideline for any state striving for a harmonious combination of economic growth, social justice, and responsible management of natural resources. In this regard, Uzbekistan's experience certainly deserves special attention.[2] A key feature of Uzbekistan's state policy in implementing the Sustainable Development Goals is the priority of upholding human honor and dignity. This principle recognizes that individuals are the highest value of society and the state; therefore, all state institutions must act with a focus on ensuring the reliable protection of their rights and freedoms. In recent years, the country has demonstrated significant progress on most of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), achieving tangible results in reducing poverty, developing the education system, protecting healthcare, promoting green energy, and improving legal institutions.

Moreover, these achievements are supported not only by economic indicators, but also by a strengthening regulatory framework, functioning parliamentary and public oversight institutions, and active participation in international initiatives, demonstrating a systemic and comprehensive approach to sustainable development. First and foremost, the country's improved position in international rankings has become an important confirmation of the effectiveness of the reforms being implemented. According to the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) 2025 report, Uzbekistan ranked 62nd globally, scoring 73 points, an improvement of 19 places compared to the previous year. This progress, achieved in a relatively short period, reflects the country's efforts to transform its economic and social model toward greater openness, inclusiveness, and sustainability. Thus, since 2017, Uzbekistan has been recognized as a leader in SDG implementation in the Central Asian and

Eastern European region, reflecting both ongoing reforms and the creation of an effective institutional and regulatory framework supporting these transformations. The legal framework for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals, which has been significantly strengthened in recent years, deserves special attention. In particular, a key step was the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 20, 2018, No. 841, "On measures to implement the National Sustainable Development Goals and Targets for the period up to 2030." [2] This document became a fundamental step in adapting the global sustainable development agenda to the country's national priorities.

Furthermore, the establishment of a special parliamentary commission to monitor the implementation of the national sustainable development goals and targets up to 2030 ensured political and legislative support for the sustainable development program, created conditions for parliamentary oversight, and engaged the parliamentary corps in the monitoring of relevant strategies and programs [2]. In this context, it is particularly noteworthy that on December 14, 2022, the UN General Assembly unanimously approved a resolution "Strengthening the role of parliaments in accelerating the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)."

The resolution was initiated by President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who proposed it in 2020 at the 75th session of the UN General Assembly [4]. This step clearly reflects Uzbekistan's commitment to the principles of global responsibility and international partnership in implementing the SDGs. Uzbekistan has identified 190 priority SDG indicators adapted to national conditions. Of these, 128 indicators are already available on the official national statistics portal (nsdg.stat.uz), including detailed data on areas such as decent work, industrialization, poverty reduction, health, and gender equality. Thus, the country ensures transparency and accessibility of statistical data to a wide range of stakeholders, which is particularly important for objectively assessing progress, identifying problem areas, and timely policy adjustments. Equally important is economic sustainability, which plays a decisive role in the implementation of most of the SDGs.

A growing economy is the main factor enabling investment in healthcare, education, infrastructure, and social protection. Over the past eight years, Uzbekistan's economy has demonstrated stable and dynamic growth: gross domestic product has more than doubled to approximately \$115 billion,¹ with projected growth reaching \$130 billion in 2025. [5]

At the same time, foreign direct investment has increased significantly, exceeding \$130 billion. This revitalization of the investment climate has been made possible by the consistent liberalization of economic policy, the creation of a favorable business environment, and the expansion of public-private partnership mechanisms. Furthermore, the country's growing financial reserves, exceeding \$48 billion for the first time, demonstrates the increased stability of the financial system and increased confidence among international investors. Uzbekistan's exports also grew, reaching \$26 billion, reflecting positive trends associated with production diversification and the expansion of national products into new markets. [5]

In this context, the important role of government programs for the development of small and medium-sized businesses is noted, providing employment for over 10 million people, stimulating entrepreneurship, and increasing household incomes. This year alone,

¹ stat.uz

approximately 9,000 new enterprises and service infrastructure facilities are planned for commissioning, with an investment volume of \$35 billion. Social sector funding for 2025 totaled approximately 19 trillion soums, confirming this priority in state policy.[1]

Achievements in human capital development, particularly in education and healthcare, are also worth highlighting. Preschool enrollment reached 78 percent, and more than 2.5 million new kindergarten places were created. Over one million additional places were created in the school system, virtually ensuring universal enrollment of school-age children.

Significant progress has also been made in higher education: student enrollment has increased from 9% to 42%, with over 50% of these students being female, demonstrating gender balance and expanding opportunities for women. Over 2,000 students are studying abroad, over 750 of whom receive state scholarships, contributing to the development of a highly qualified generation of specialists.

In healthcare, the availability and quality of medical services have been improved. Funding has increased sixfold, and over 400 types of high-tech procedures have become available to residents of the regions. Life expectancy has increased from 73.8 to 75.1 years, indicating positive changes in the healthcare system².

The government has set an ambitious goal of increasing the share of renewable energy sources to 54% by 2030, attracting approximately \$35 billion in investment into the sector. In addition, the "Yashil Makon" environmental program is being implemented, aimed at large-scale greening of areas, forest restoration, and raising environmental awareness among the population, thereby contributing to the development of "green" cities with a high level of environmental safety.[2]

To sum up, I would like to make the following conclusions. First, Uzbekistan is demonstrating comprehensive progress in implementing the Sustainable Development Goals, covering key areas – economic, social, and environmental.

Second, strengthening the legal and regulatory framework and creating institutional mechanisms ensure a systemic and consistent approach to achieving the goals. Third, transparency and accessibility of data facilitate objective assessment of results and timely policy adjustments.

Thus, Uzbekistan's sustainable development exemplifies the successful combination of reforms, institutional support, and international cooperation, which inspires confidence in achieving the SDGs by 2030 and creating an exemplary development path for the region. Participation in this session will demonstrate Uzbekistan's role as an active and responsible player in the international arena, ready to share its unique experience while adopting best global practices to achieve comprehensive and harmonious development..

List of references:

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² stat.uz

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